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Intelligence and Emotional Maturity as Predictors of Marital Adjustment Among Women

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar **

The present study was conducted on an incidental-cum-purposive sample of 100 married women respondents belonging to Patna town. The main purpose was to examine the influence of intelligence and emotional maturity on marital adjustment amongst the respondents. It was hypothesized that : There would be a significant effect of (i) intelligence and (ii) emotional maturity on the marital adjustment of the respondents, (iii) there would be significant relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity of the respondents. Marital adjustment, intelligence and emotional maturity were measured using MAQ by Kumar and Rohtagi, Mohsin's GIT and Singh and Bhargawa's EMS respectively. Besides, a Personal Data Sheet was used to get other necessary information about the respondents. The Scales along with PDS were employed on the respondents and data were recorded as per the direction of the manuals concerned. The data were analysed using t-test and Pearson 'r'. The results confirmed the hypotheses. It was found that (i) high intelligent and (ii) emotionally matured female respondents manifested sound marital adjustment. Further, intelligence and emotional maturity were found significantly and positively correlated.

Introduction

In the present circumstances, married women are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are giving rise to many psychosomatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in day to day life. So, the study of emotional life is now emerging as a descriptive science, comparable with anatomy. It deals with an interplay of forces with intensifies and quantities. Available tests are crude and measure chiefly the degree of dependence. But this test measures the different aspects of emotional maturity. As self acceptance is an important aspect of maturity says Wenkart, and it must be preceded by acceptance from others.

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Present study embodies concepts like intelligence, marital adjustment and emotional maturity. Intelligence is the aggregate or global capacity of the individual to act purposefully, to think rationally and to deal effectively with one's environment (Wechsler, 1939, p. 3).

Marriage is the opportunity a person for secure and protected satisfaction of one's needs for companionship affection and sexual expression involving most intimate type of emotional relationship between two individual (Coleman, 1964). Emotional maturity refers to self-control to manage one's own emotion and work to understand them. Actually, emotional maturity is not only the effective determinant of personality pattern but it also helps to control the growth of development. The concept "Mature" emotional behaviour of any level is that which reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control, who is able to broke delay and to suffer without self-pity, might still. According' to another author seoul, if the emotional development of the individual is relatively complete, his adaptability is high, his regressive tendencies are low, and his vulnerability is minimal. Therefore the emotionally mature is not who necessarily has resolved all conditions that aroused anxiety and hostility but it is continuously in process of seeing himself in clearer perspective, continuously involved in a struggle to gain healthy integration of feeling, thinking action. There are few studies relating to examine the effect of intelligence and emotional maturity on marital adjustment amongst the women respondents. The present attempt is to fill-up the gap in this connection. This justifies the undertaking of the present endeavour.

Objectives

There were objectives of the present study : To examine the influence of (i) intelligence (ii) EM on marital adjustment and, (iii) to examine the relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity.

Hypotheses

- (i) There would be significant effect of intelligence and emotional maturity on marital adjustment amongst the respondents.
- (ii) There would be a significant relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity.

Method of Study

Sample Used

The study was conducted on 100 married women respondents belonging to Patna using incidental-cum-purposive sampling technique. The respondents were matched as far as practicable.

Research Tools Used

- Marital Adjustment Questionnaire by Kumar, P. & Rohatogi was used to measure marital adjustment of the respondents.
- Mohsin's General Intelligence Test was used to measure the intelligence of the married women respondents.
- Singh and Bhargawa's Emotional Maturity Scale was used to measure the emotional maturity of the married women respondents.
- A PDS was used to get other necessary information relating to married women respondents.

Procedure of Data Collection

The Scales along with PDS were employed on the respondents and informations were gathered. Using median cut, respondents were divided into high and low intelligence groups and high and low emotional maturity groups respectively. All the groups of respondents were compared in respect of marital adjustment.

Results and interpretation

Table-01

t-ratio showing the effect of intelligence on marital adjustment of the respondents.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	df	p
Intelligence	High	45	73.29	3.93	10.75	98	<.01
	Low	55	82.64	4.80			

It is obvious from the table 01 that respondents belonging to high groups in intelligence showed sound marital adjustment as compared to their counterparts belonging to low groups. ($t = 10.50$, $df = 98$, $p < .01$). Thus, first hypothesis is confirmed. The finding relating to intelligence might be interpreted on the ground of greater tolerance on the part of respondents belonging to high intelligence group than the respondents belonging to low intelligence group leading to manifest sound marital adjustment.

Table-02

t-ratio showing the effect of intelligence on emotional maturity on mental adjustment.

Variables	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	df	p
Emotional Maturity	High	42	70.92	3.97	10.04	98	< .01
	Low	58	80.36	3.98			

Further, the results of table-02 clearly revealed the fact that high emotional maturity groups of married women manifested comparatively sound marital adjustment than their low emotional maturity group of married women [$t = 10.04$; $df = 98$; $p < .01$]. Thus, hypothesis no. 02 is retained. Results relating to emotional maturity might be interpreted on the ground of better control on emotion on the part of high emotionally matured person leading to manifest sound marital adjustment.

Table-03
r-showing the relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity of the respondents.

Variables	N	r	df	p
Intelligence Vs Emotional Maturity	100	0.483	98	<.01

The results displayed in table-03 showed significant relationship between intelligence and emotional maturity ($r = 0.483$, $df = 98$, $p < .01$). Thus, third hypothesis is confirmed.

Conclusions

- (i) High intelligence is conducive to manifest sound marital adjustment.
- (ii) High emotional maturity leads sound marital adjustment.
- (iii) Intelligence and emotional maturity are positively and significantly correlated.

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